

Language and Artificial Intelligence for Sustainable Development in Global Economy: The Chinese Perspective

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Abstract

In our contemporary times, the advent of science and technology and its innovative foundations of digital learning and accelerated knowledge explosion in global circles, have given rise to many developmental processes, of which artificial intelligence is one. Though this program was created by humans, through programming and algorithms with specialized skills- especially in the area of language translation- it has almost overtaken the era of human knowledge which is fast dwindling, paving way for AI, a powerful tool for diverse knowledge and global innovations. The study establishes a synergy between language and artificial intelligence, placing language as pivotal in the mechanics of artificial intelligence. The methodology adopts a qualitative method of descriptive analysis of related researches, with quantitative statistical information supporting the study; using China as a case study. Results show a complementary relationship between language and AI in key developmental areas, such as service delivery and manufacturing reforms, using language (words and symbols) as the principal element with which AI functions, for sustainable human development.

Keywords: *Language, Natural Intelligence, Artificial Intelligence, Sustainability, Sustainable Development, Global Economy, Chinese Economy.*

INTRODUCTION

Natural and artificial intelligence (AI) in recent times, have become a focal point in our dynamic societies. The interplay of these areas of knowledge have proved indispensable, to a reasonable extent; in the dissemination of knowledge. (Fingelkurts &Fingelkurts, 2004; Freeman, 2001). There is evidently a symbiotic and mutual relationship between language and intelligence-natural or artificial-because knowledge and intelligence are encoded in language.

Fromkin et al (2013) view language as an expression of ideas, using speech- sounds, combined into words. Words are combined into sentences to express ideas and thoughts. Language serves as the primary tool for artificial intelligence (in human communication-enabling AI systems), which interpret and generate human-like responses, essential for the performance of language-related tasks with increasing efficiency and accuracy. Artificial intelligence (AI) refers to the ability of a digital computer or computer-controlled robot to perform tasks, commonly associated with intelligent beings (Robinson,2018).Artificial intelligence has revolutionized language interactions, such as translation, language education and text analysis, to evolve innovative and sustainable developmental processes that positively impact on service delivery (Zhang &Aslan,2021).

The synergy between language and artificial intelligence is aptly described in the words of Sokolowski (1988:48) that ‘artificial intelligence does not imply mimicking the brain and the nervous system, it transforms, codifies and manipulates written discourse.... Writing comes between the brain and the computer’.

Language and AI has given a boost to cross-border communication and collaboration, creating significant effects on global economies and stimulating economic growth on a global scale (Malnovic, 2016). Global economy refers to the multifaceted international economic activities and exchanges that transcend national borders, integrate marketing and foster interdependence among countries for sustainability. The study explores the synergy of language and artificial intelligence as it impacts on global sustainability, using China as a case study. China is notably among the global economies that have leveraged on language and AI for innovative growth in every aspect of her economy. Some other economies include Canada and the United States. The significant strides in both AI development and language in China has compelled researchers to undertake related studies in this area (Singh et al,2013; Lopez, 2020; Yu et al, 2012; Frankish & Ramsey,2014; Xiao & Guo, 2020; Nwachukwu,2021; Lee et al, 2020; Kaplan,2016; Umeano and Enemuo,2020; Guzman & Lewis, 2020; Jiang et al,2022). Zhang & Duang (2020) opine that China's technological advancements and government support, have fostered an environment conducive to the growth of AI driving language services.

China's AI- powered language technologies have maximized domestic economic growth, expanded international communication, and have positively influenced the global economy. China's economy is one of the world's economies that have experienced rapid growth and transformation in recent years. As at the year 2024, her grossly domestic products GPP was 134,908.4 billion yuan, up by 5.0 percent over the previous year, with a gross national income of 133,967.2 a 5.1 percent increase from 2023(National bureau of Statistics of China, 2025). This transformation could be traced back to her implementation of some economic reforms in 1978. According to Ogunkola and Bankole (2021), Chinese economic reforms shifted from a centralized to a market-based economy, making it the world's second largest economy and a major player in global trade and investments. Moreover, her GDP growth has averaged over 9% a year and almost 800 million people have been alleviated from poverty.

Gill and Kharas (2007) observe that China's strong economic growth is based on several factors, such as adoption of market-oriented reforms, increased foreign investment and export-oriented manufacturing, as well as integration of artificial intelligence. In line with the United Nations Sustainable goals, China outlined the New Generation AI Development Plan (2017) aimed at leading AI research, applications, and talent development by 2030. AI applications in China covers *Smart Cities* for urban management, traffic control and public safety, *healthcare AI*, *e-commerce*, *manufacturing with robots* and predictive maintenance to enhance efficiency (Yu et al,2012). The giant strides of economic reforms in China were made possible by the use of language in the pursuit of urbanization and industrialization policies, leading to a significant expansion of *service* and *manufacturing* reforms (Xiao & Guo, 2020).

The digital economy of China is immensely dependent on the advancement of artificial intelligence powered language processing technologies, with prominent technology giants like Baidu, Alibaba and Tencent at the forefront of innovation. Nwachukwu et al (2021) note that these Chinese technological companies have successfully developed voice assistants, smart customer service solutions and personalized content recommendation system that cater for the specific needs of the Chinese consumers. Accordingly, the efficiency and effectiveness of her digital economy have been significantly enhanced, thereby contributing to the nation's overall economic growth. Many researches have been done in the area of artificial intelligence and global development, but extant literature reveals that not much attention has been given to the area of language in the processing of artificial intelligence. This is the lacuna that this study intends to fill.

Research Questions

1. What are the language-based AI research innovations in China?
2. Has AI made any impact on the development of the Chinese work force?
3. What cultural exchange has China recorded with other nations, in the area of artificial intelligence?
4. What are the challenges of language and artificial intelligence in China?
5. How can language and artificial intelligence be enhanced in China and the global economy?

METHODOLOGY

The study adopts a qualitative methodology, using relevant journal articles and researches, with quantitative statistical instances; in establishing the synergy between language and artificial intelligence, particularly in the Chinese economy. The choice of China as a case study is based on her demonstration of an increasing ingenuity and innovation in exploring avenues of maximizing her national growth, by leveraging on technological advancements in our contemporary times. More emphasis is placed on the various language applications such as smart system, virtual assisted applications that have brought innovation and growth in viable areas of her economy, such as the *manufacturing* and *service* sectors, research and economic policies that have culminated in making China an economic giant on the global scene.

RESULTS

Table 3: Output of Major Industrial Products and Growth Rates of the Industrial Enterprises above the Designated Size in 2024^[22]

Product	Unit	Output	Increase over 2023 (%)
Yarn	10000 tons	2277.9	1.3
Cloth	100 million meters	306.3	2.2
Chemical fiber	10000 tons	7910.8	9.7
Refined sugar (final product)	10000 tons	1498.6	17.0
Cigarettes	100 million	24654.6	0.9
Color TV sets	10000	20745.4	4.6
Household refrigerators	10000	10395.7	8.3
Air conditioners	10000	26598.4	9.7
Crude steel	10000 tons	100509.1	-1.7
Rolled steel ^[23]	10000 tons	139967.4	1.1
Ten kinds of nonferrous metals	10000 tons	7918.8	4.3
Of which: Refined copper (copper)	10000 tons	1364.4	4.1
Aluminum electrolyze	10000 tons	4400.5	4.6
Cement	100 million tons	18.3	-9.5
Sulfuric acid (100%)	10000 tons	10369.9	6.9
Caustic soda (100%)	10000 tons	4365.7	5.5
Ethylene	10000 tons	3493.4	0.7
Chemical fertilizer (100 percent equivalent)	10000 tons	6006.1	8.5
Power generation equipment	10000 kilowatts	28433.9	16.0
Motor vehicles	10000	3155.9	4.8
Of which: New energy vehicles	10000	1316.8	38.7
Integrated circuits	100 million pieces	4514.2	22.2
Mobile telephones	10000	166952.9	7.8
Micro computer equipment	10000	33912.9	2.7
Industrial robots	10000 sets	55.6	14.2
Ultra-clear glass for solar industry	10000 square meters	287884.5	53.5
Charging piles	10000	469.7	58.7
Smart watches	10000	8095.4	5.4
Virtual reality devices	10000	836.6	59.4

Figure I: Major industrial growth of China

(Culled from reports of the National bureau of Statistics of China,2025)

From the above table, amongst other major industrial products in Chinese economic growth rate in 2024, is the virtual reality rates, representing (59.45%) and industrial robots (4.8%). This goes to show China's huge dependence on AI and internet technologies for her visible innovative economic growth. These virtual and artificial intelligence-driven processes are encoded in language, using written symbols.

Table 14: Total Value of Foreign Direct Investment and the Growth Rates in 2024

Sector	Enterprises	Increase over 2023 (%)	Actually Utilized Value (100 million yuan)	Increase over 2023 (%)
Total	59080	9.9	8263	-27.1
Of which:				
Agriculture, Forestry, Animal Husbandry and Fishery	374	-10.5	27	-46.0
Manufacturing	3871	6.8	2212	-30.4
Production and Supply of Electricity, Heat Power, Gas and Water	439	-22.7	284	-10.9
Transport, Storage and Post	838	-3.3	112	-25.0
Information Transmission, Software and Information Technology Services	3988	6.0	526	-53.6
Wholesale and Retail	20854	15.8	584	-15.4
Real Estate	612	-10.5	406	-49.9
Leasing and Business Services	11158	4.5	1815	-0.2
Household Services, Repair and Other Services	859	18.3	35	3.6

Figure 2: Value added investments and growth in China

(Culled from National Bureau of Statistics of China, 2025)

Similar to Figure 1, results on the value added and growth rates of industrial enterprises, show a progressive growth of 6.1% in China's manufacturing sector between 2020-2024, with imports and exports across the globe, in addition to added value from other related sectors like mining, water, electricity and gas.

Table 13: Imports and Exports of Goods with Major Countries and Regions, Growth Rates and Proportions in 2024

Country or region	Exports (100 million yuan)	Increase over 2023 (%)	Proportion of the total (%)	Imports (100 million yuan)	Increase over 2023 (%)	Proportion of the total (%)
ASEAN	41736	13.4	16.4	28163	3.2	15.3
European Union	36751	4.3	14.4	19164	-3.3	10.4
United States	37337	6.1	14.7	11641	1.2	6.3
Republic of Korea	10415	-0.5	4.1	12931	13.6	7.0
Hong Kong, China	20719	7.3	8.1	1321	37.8	0.7
Japan	10816	-2.3	4.2	11119	-1.7	6.0
Taiwan, China	5350	11.0	2.1	15498	10.5	8.4
Russia	8212	5.0	3.2	9198	1.0	5.0
Brazil	5128	23.3	2.0	8258	-4.4	4.5
India	8574	3.6	3.4	1280	-1.7	0.7
South Africa	1552	-6.5	0.6	2180	-3.0	1.2

Figure 3: Chinese collaboration with global economies

(Culled from National Bureau of Statistics of China, 2025)

Figure 3 shows the significant collaboration of China and major countries in the global economy -the European Union, United States of America, Japan, Hong Kong, South Africa and others- in 2024. Each of these countries has leveraged on the growing AI-assisted industrial advancements of China in various sectors, through significant imports and exports which have progressively increased each year-including information transfer- with sustainable impact on the global economy. This sustainable development in global circles is traceable to artificial intelligence and language.

FINDINGS

Research Question One: What are the language based AI research innovations in China?

Artificial intelligence and communication research is increasingly closing up, as AI technologies are taking over communicative roles in virtually every aspect of human endeavor in China. There are extensive AI language research and innovations by her institutions, focusing on a wide array of language and AI sub fields, including machine translations, sentiment analysis and conversational AI.

Xiao & Guo (2020) observe that the outcome of such research has far reaching potentials to economic growth through innovative applications in areas such as automated language translation and social media.

AI language applications

In China, AI language applications such as chat box, visual assistant, Chat GPT, Ask - AI are increasingly in use. Hohenstein et al (2023) opine that these language applications produce different forms of language -from text messages to social media posts, computer programs and speeches – in answering questions and offering varieties of responses across many fields of human endeavor, such as education, e-commerce, manufacturing and customer service; as well as other service areas.

AI technologies are taking over communicative roles in virtually every discipline. For example, the smart reply system is grossly significant and applicable in text responses and varieties of written contexts. It helps users to compose messages in minutes. These innovations have advanced the Chinese economy significantly, compared to others.

Digital and natural processing technology

The digital economy of China is immensely dependent on the advancement of artificial intelligence powered language processing technologies, with prominent technology giants like Baidu, Alibaba and Tencent at the forefront of innovation.

These technological companies have developed advanced natural language processing (NLP) capabilities that enable seamless communication between humans and machines, thereby leading to the growth of various sectors, including e-commerce, Fintech and online entertainment (Guzman & Lewis,2020).

Nwachukwu et al (2021) note that the Chinese technological companies have successfully developed voice assistants, smart customer service solutions and personalized content recommendation system that cater for the specific needs of the Chinese consumers. Accordingly, efficiency and effectiveness of her digital economy is enhanced, thereby contributing to the nation's overall economic growth.

Research Question Two: Has AI made any impact on the development of the Chinese work force?

Artificial intelligence plays a vital role in enhancing English language proficiency among the Chinese work force, preparing them for the challenges of global collaboration and business communication. Various AI driven language learning platforms accord personalized, interactive and engaging language learning experiences to her workforce.

Hohenstein et al observe that AI applications such as chat box, chat GPT, visual assistants and Ask AI has increasingly enhanced language learning. These applications have produced answers to queries in the workplace and have offered many options in text messages and social media posts, computer programs and speeches.

Similarly, Odinko (2021) opines that AI powered platforms play an important part in workers' development, equipping workers with language skills necessary for success in global economy, thereby supporting economic growth.

Research Question Three: What cultural exchange has China recorded with other nations, in the area of artificial intelligence?

AI technology serves as key facilitators of language and cultural exchange between China and other nations. According to Jin and Lin (2019), the cross-cultural understanding and international trade relationship between China and other nations have been made possible by artificial intelligence powered translation tools.

Improved communication between Chinese businesses and their global counterparts, enable smoother negotiations, more effective collaboration, and increased opportunities for business growth. Furthermore, such AI driven language solutions promote tourism, cultural exchange, and sharing of knowledge and ideas between China and international communities, thereby enhancing the nation's global standing and economic prospects.

Research question Four: What are the challenges of language and artificial intelligence in China?

The integration of language and artificial intelligence in global economies, specifically in China, is not devoid of setbacks and challenges. Some of the challenges include:

Linguistic diversity

This is one of the basic challenges confronting the relationship between language and artificial intelligence in the economy of China, presenting obstacles in communication and technology.

The Mandarin Chinese serves as the official language in China, although China has numerous regional languages and dialects that complicate the development and implementation of AI systems, and reliance on AI language processing capabilities.

These challenges, particularly pronounced as language-based systems; often struggle to accurately interpret and generate speech and text in non-Mandarian languages (Umeano and Enemuo, 2020).

Accordingly, this diversity limits the effectiveness of AI in promoting linguistic inclusivity and exacerbates the digital divide between Mandarin and non-Mandarian speaking populations, thereby reinforcing social inequalities and hindering economic growth.

Data privacy and security

Data privacy and security constitutes another critical challenge and concern in integrating language and AI within the Chinese economy. As AI systems increase vast amount of textural data to perform functions, such as machine translation, sentiment analysis and speech recognition; concerns surrounding the protection of personal information and intellectual property rights become eminent, thus posing challenges in language and artificial intelligence processes in the economy.

Limited skilled force

China's limited skilled force is another inhibiting area in language and artificial intelligence. With the rapid development of AI technologies, there is an increasing disparity in demand and supply for AI talents in the country, resulting in limited workforce. Nurturing a skilled work force to support language-AI integration therefore, becomes a daunting task. Yu et al (2012).

Job displacement

Job displacement also poses a significant challenge, arising from the integration of language and artificial intelligence in Chinese economy. As artificial intelligence systems become more adept at processing language and automating tasks, they risk rendering certain job roles redundant, particularly within industries -such as customer service translation and content creation (Singh et al, 2013).

Kaplan (2016) remarks that the potential for job loss and its ramifications on income inequality, poverty and social stability are crucial considerations for policy makers.

The relationship between language and artificial intelligence in the economy of China ultimately, faces the setback of AI driven job placement.

Intellectual property protection

Another problem facing the workability of language and artificial intelligence in the Chinese economy is the issue of protecting intellectual property rights for artificial intelligence technologies and language- related innovations. This stems from the existence of intellectual thefts /piracy, thereby posing problems in developing and enforcing effective intellectual property laws that encourage innovation, while deterring infringement.

Research question Five How can language and artificial intelligence be enhanced in China and the global economy?

Although the relationship between language and artificial intelligence in the economy of China has made significant progress, there is still room for improvement, which will positively impact on global economies.

The following measures are recommended:

Multilingual artificial intelligence capabilities

This entails fostering the development of natural language processing (NLP) algorithms that effectively understand and generate texts in multiple Chinese dialects, Canadian dialects and other global languages (Makridakis,2017). Ezeoha and Olise (2022) uphold that this practice encourages collaboration between linguists, technological developers and AI specialists and researchers; in an effort to create comprehensive multilingual AI solutions.

International collaboration

International collaboration is another viable measure in fostering partnership with foreign universities, research institutions, and technological companies to exchange knowledge, best practices, and resources in AI development. Furthermore, it encompasses participation in different fora and initiatives, related to AI ethics, regulations, and standardization; such as global partnership in artificial intelligence. This measure facilitates collaboration on AI projects, tackles global challenges and promotes mutual learning.

Inclusive language policies

The sustainable relationship between language and artificial intelligence in the Chinese economy, as well as other economies; could be enhanced through the implementation of inclusive language policies. This encourages businesses and organizations to adopt inclusive language practices in artificial intelligence, thereby creating a more equitable linguistic landscape (Jiang et al,2022).It also ensures that AI systems represent various dialects, minority languages and foreign languages, spoken in China and other economies, such as Canada and other nations of the world.

Intellectual property rights protection

Adequate protection of language and AI centrist intellectual property is another way of boosting language and artificial intelligence processes. This could be achieved through public enlightenment programs, stressing the protection of intellectual language and property writing in AI, as well as strengthening intellectual property laws and enforcement mechanisms, to protect AI innovations and language-related technologies (Lopez et al, 2020).

Additionally, investing in educational training programs to nurture skilled professionals who can work on AI- language integration is imperative in this area, as well as promoting inter disciplinary researches by linguistics and artificial intelligence experts, to drive innovations and promote deeper understanding of language in this context, for global development.

Regulatory framework

Another means of strengthening the relationship between language and artificial intelligence in China and the global economy at large, is by setting up a regulatory framework. The lack of a comprehensive regulatory framework for AI in Chinese industries, impedes investment and innovation. Clear guidance and standards are necessary in providing a supportive environment for research, development, and commercialization of AI applications. This may involve updating existing regulations or creating new ones to address AI-specific concerns, such as intellectual property rights and others.

CONCLUSION

The study establishes the mutual relationship between language and artificial intelligence- in global economies such as China- as each contributes to the growth and development of the other.

Language serves as the primary means for processing artificial intelligence, its understanding and human communication, enabling AI systems to interpret and generate human-like responses, which are very essential in performing language- related tasks, such as translation, speech recognition and text analysis, with increased efficiency and accuracy.

Similarly, artificial intelligence has revolutionized the way we interact with language, transforming industries in areas of language translation, education, and text analysis.

This synergy between language and AI ultimately, enhances communication and collaboration, thereby impacting on global economies and stimulating economic growth.

Language and artificial intelligence are no longer confined to the fringe of technological innovation. It has impacted significantly on the global economic landscape, driving productivity and efficiency gains, fostering new opportunities for international trade, and transition toward service economies, especially in the Chinese economy.

On a macroeconomic level, the synergy of language and artificial intelligence can boost productivity growth, leading to increase economic growth and new opportunities for international trade. These could serve as a powerful engine for economic expansion, adding a new dimension to global trade. Moreover, language is a sine qua non to amplifying the shift towards service- based economies.

On a micro level, language and artificial intelligence have positive impacts in the development and management of global value chains (GVCs) which improve predictions of future trends, risk management and the enhancement of efficiency and global sustainability.

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